

Personally Meaningful Experience in the Context of Product Use

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Abstract

Humans have an innate need to assign meaning to elements of their immediate environment and to the flow of events in their lives. This research study explores the ways in which digital products can actively support the creation and maintenance of life meanings. The market for such products is expanding rapidly, yet designers and researchers have little or no understanding of designing for aspirational product use. This paper reports the results of an initial pilot study of this novel user experience research area.

Key words: meaningful experience, life meaning, concept development

Introduction

Personally meaningful experience can be described as an interaction between a current sensory experience and several life-meaning constructs such as self-worth, efficacy in the world, sense of purpose, and personal values. Products that assist consumers in managing such life meanings are increasingly in demand. One indicator of this phenomenon is the annual spending for self-improvement products and services. Americans, for example, spent \$5.71 billion in 2000 on these products and services [Marketdata, 2001], with the two biggest categories being motivational/spiritual/self-help products (\$1.8 billion) and exercise/weight-loss products (\$2.3 billion).

This self-improvement market segment is expected to persist and perhaps increase. Norton [2003] has traced the rising consumer demand for meaningful product experiences from the 1970's to the present, suggesting that a gradual eroding of community and family networks has forced individuals to process life meanings and personal values in new ways. Naming this phenomenon "The Transformation Economy," Pine and Gilmore [1999] predict that consumers will increasingly seek products and services which promote personally meaningful experiences. These product and service providers will explicitly help consumers achieve personal goals, whether these goals center on new expressions of personal identity or instantiations of personal values.

In the face of this customer demand, however, product development teams know little about the aspirational aspects of product use. This paper reports on a preliminary pilot study exploring both users' conceptions of personally meaningful experience and their impressions of possible digital products that would stimulate enhanced experiences of life meaning. The research questions underlying this pilot study have been designed to begin the process of better understanding this research area:

- What product-related behaviors do users associate with personally meaningful experience?
- What product affordances and features do users associate with such an experience?
- In what product-use situations would consumers want or expect personally meaningful experiences?
- What are the common subjective elements within users' accounts of personally meaningful experience in the context of product use?

The answers to these questions could help guide designers to improve both the lives of product users and product design itself, by supporting the emotional imperative to construct coherent life meanings.

The next two sections of this paper will explore the theoretical foundations of personally meaningful experience in the context of product use. The subsequent section will outline the methods used in the study. The final section will present the findings of the pilot stage of a larger study and the implications of this study for product design.

Personally Meaningful Experience and Product Use

Humans have an innate ability to assign meaning to things, people, and situations. From a young age we have associated concepts, words, and feeling states with objects; differentiated types of familial relationships and their implications for behavior; and recognized opportunities for learning, for bonding, and for play [Jung, 1964].

Baumeister [1991] suggests that this ability to generate and manage meaning serves two essential functions: adaptation to the environment and self-regulation of behavior and emotions. At its most basic level, meaning-making can be defined as “recognizing signals and patterns in the environment.” Environmental patterns are often complex, especially those with social dimensions. Humans, both individually and collectively, have responded to this complexity by developing the capacity to construct intricate meaning structures, an ability which has resulted in cultures that are rich with knowledge, art, and technology. Meaning is one way we bring order to the chaos of phenomenal experience.

Meaning is also integral to the regulation of emotional states. In their foundational work, Schacter and Singer [1964] observed that emotional episodes are a combination of a feeling state (bodily arousal) and an associated meaning structure or label. More recent theories stress the situated aspect of emotion, in which such factors as events (external or internal), meaning structures (interpretations), action potential, and behavior interact to produce emotional episodes [Gross, 1998; Power and Dagher, 1999].

Life meanings. Humans have a basic need to create an ongoing sense of coherence from the many situations in their lives. Frankl [1988] called this need the “will-to-meaning,” describing it as the primary motivating drive to determine an overarching purpose or thematic resonance within our life events. Frankl believed that an individual’s life meaning is emergent and dynamic, in a constant process of being refined in response to ongoing experience [1986]. In this model, life meaning is often defined in unitary terms, with individuals driven to find the central purpose to their lives.

Baumeister [1991], in contrast to Frankl’s unitary approach, has suggested that life meanings are distributed across four categories of experience or “needs for meaning.” These needs for meaning are:

1. Purpose, to see one’s actions oriented toward a purpose, to interpret one’s current activities in light of a future or possible states.
2. Values, to have an enlivened set of values to guide thoughts and behavior, to feel that one’s actions are good and right and justifiable.
3. Efficacy, to experience a sense of control over the events in one’s life, to see that one’s actions are making a difference.
4. Self-worth, to experience one’s self as having worth or positive value, to find a basis for determining positive value.

These needs for meaning may not be equally important to any single individual at a given time, nor are they consistently important over the course of a single person’s life. Yet, because they are integral to adaptation to the environment and to emotional regulation, these needs serve as primary motivators in the many contexts of human life.

Personally meaningful experience. For the purposes of this research, personally meaningful experience is being defined as *a positively-valenced interaction between an existing sensory experience and one or more of the four life-meaning constructs*. A positively-valenced experience [Watson, 2002] refers to an experience that an individual identifies as affirming or uplifting. Here is one example of a personally meaningful experience in the context of product use:

Sue, a woman in her 40’s, is casually surfing the Internet and unexpectedly comes across a current photo of an old friend from high school. Sue is suddenly struck by how much

she herself has matured since high school and experiences a positive sense of elevated self-worth and life satisfaction.

The existing sensory experience in this example is Sue seeing the photo on the web page. The life-meaning constructs are self-worth, one's life having a positive value, and efficacy, to see that one's actions are making a difference. In this example, the sensory experience triggers an evaluative process that activates and perhaps modifies the self-worth and efficacy life-meaning constructs. In this way, personally meaningful experience has been generated.

Park and Folkman [1997] have suggested that changes in one's life meaning constructs occur when the significance assigned to current sensory experience reaches the appropriate threshold, resulting in an attempt to reconcile the situational meaning assigned to current experience with global or life meaning constructs. Sue's positive modification of the self-worth life meaning construct is the result of such a reconciliation process.

We access life-meaning constructs frequently throughout the course of a day. The choice of what we wear, for example, is often based on needs related to life meaning, whether that is a desire to influence others or the expression of some particular aspect of individual or group identity. Similarly, we often base our buying decisions about music, food, and entertainment on what is personally meaningful [Schmidt, 1999].

The next section describes the ways in which humans necessarily engage environmental features in the process of constructing or modifying life meanings.

The Human Capacity to Use Objects to Process Life Meaning

The previous scenario, Sue and the web site photo, also highlights an important proposition underlying this study: the human use of external objects in the life meaning process. Sue interacted with a desktop computer and as a result assessed her life in a positive way. This section touches on the root causes of such an event, through an exploration of the role of objects in everyday human life, and in the perceptual process itself.

Life meaning as a self-object transaction. Csikszentmihalyi and Rochberg-Halton [1981] engaged in an ethnographic study of humans and their everyday household objects, seeking to

“examine the role of objects in people’s definition of who they are, who they have been, and who they wish to become.” They found that people experience complex structures of meaning in everyday objects through a *transactional* process involving directed attention, perception, and goals or intentions. This transactional model of meaning-making via external objects clearly privileges higher-level life meanings. These authors suggest that such transactions with objects play an integral part in the ongoing process of identity formation, connecting the inward sense of individuality with a greater social self.

Life meaning as a self-environment transaction. This propensity toward using objects to construct life meanings may be related to a more elemental use of environmental features in the perceptual process itself. Ecological psychologists posit that perception and cognition occur in an individual who is dynamically coupled with her or his environment: “Perceiving is an achievement of the individual, not an appearance in the theater of the mind” [Heft, 2001]. It is a keeping-in-touch with the world, an experiencing of things, rather than a having of experiences.

From this perspective, the very act of perception couples aspects of the environment with information processing, in turn influencing cognitive processes such as memory [Greeno, 1991] and learning [Maturana, 1980]. Gibson [1979], however, made a clear distinction between perceptual meaning and abstract concepts such as value or sense of purpose. Perceptual meanings, or affordances, are properties of the environment that are perceived as potential functionalities, as opportunities for action. In Gibson’s model, perceiving the environment is a process of recognizing and selecting those affordances that are relevant to current goals.

Affordances, however, frequently occur in bundles or sets, especially those related to tools or devices [Allen, 1996]. A PDA, for example, offers numerous affordances simultaneously, from storing information to real-time communication with others. These sets of affordances may reach a threshold in complexity where conceptual meanings are required to monitor and unpack them for use. In such cases, perceptual meanings become inextricably coupled with conceptual meanings and the link between environmental affordances and personally meaningful experience is forged.

To summarize, humans have an innate ability to assign meaning to objects, people, and situations. They are driven to construct life meanings which help bring coherence and order to the many events in their lives. In their quest for personally meaningful experience, they actively use elements of the environment, especially familiar household items.

Battarbee and Mattelmaki [2002] described a number of conditions by which people form deep emotional bonds with products ranging from guitars to automobiles. They suggest that a meaningful experience involving a product is one trigger for the formation of human-product bonding. The current research differs from Battarbee and Mattelmaki's study in that this study explores the ways in which users actively pursue personally meaningful experience from their interaction with products.

The following section of this paper outlines the methods of this pilot study of user's expectations and preference for personally meaningful experience in the context of product use.

Methods

The generative research paradigm, as employed in product development research, draws heavily from three research traditions: applied anthropology, participatory design, and marketing research [Sanders, 2000]. Researchers employing this paradigm use methods such as ethnographic interviewing and participative design processes to uncover user's values, emotional associations, behaviors, and beliefs related to potential or existing products [Stapper and Sanders, 2004]. This section describes a research design influenced by the generative research tradition.

Participants. Three participants were recruited for this pilot stage. They were two females and one male with the ages of 49, 37, and 32 respectively. They all had graduate degrees in either business, technical communication, or intercultural communication. They averaged 12 years of email use, and made regular use of both a desktop computer and at least two mobile digital devices, which included laptop computers, cell phones, and PDA's. Table 1 offers specific details on each of the participants

Table 1. Demographic details of the Personally Meaningful Experience Pilot Study

Pseudonym	Age	Professional Degree	E-mail Use
Cathy	49	Intercultural Communication (PhD)	14 years
Georgia	37	Technical Communication (MS)	13 years
Jim	32	Business (MBA)	10 years

Each of these participants met three fundamental inclusion criteria for this study:

- Interest in self-improvement media relating to fitness and weight loss, to religious, spiritual topics and philosophical topics, or to improving life skills. Participants having such interests would be more likely to access and express personally meaningful experiences during the interview process.
- Informal or formal experience with two-dimensional design activities such as drawing or painting. Participants with such experience would be more likely to engage the collage activity successfully.
- Use of a desktop computer and at least one mobile digital device. Participants using multiple digital devices might be better able to imagine novel product uses in multiple locations.

Object interview: Participants had been instructed to bring a household object with them to the session that was “important to you or special in some way.” The researcher asked semi-structured, open-ended questions about the types of subjective experience the object evoked, and why the participant valued the object.

Collage construction: Participants were then asked to create a graphic representation of how they would respond to a product that gave them “the same experience” they had with their object. The researcher used the participant’s language from the object interview to describe the types of experiences the product would give them.

Participants were given a set of 120 pre-selected images and instructed to create a word-and-picture collage of this potential product-use scenario. After having selected photos from the photo set, participants arranged the photos on a page and then added words of description or explanation.

Collage debriefing interview. Participants were first asked to provide a narrative account of their collage-building process and then were debriefed on their collages. The researcher asked them to describe the various elements of the collage and how these elements interacted. Participants were then asked to draw their potential product and then to describe when and how they would use it.

Data Analysis. The collages themselves were not analyzed in this study, serving instead to stimulate discussion. Field notes from the three interviews served as the principal data and were analyzed using principles from qualitative coding [Boyatzis, 1998; Eliot et al., 2005]. Field notes were coded for text structures related to the research questions and the codes were then aggregated into central themes. These themes will next be reported as the principal findings of this pilot study.

Findings

Each of the participants completed the study tasks with relative ease. They all talked about an important object, created a collage depicting meaningful product use, drew their imagined product, and talked about the specifics of such product use. Participants in this study envisioned their potential products as having capabilities and features that purposively and predictably supported meaningful experience. This section contains aggregate descriptions of these capabilities and features:

Product capabilities

Expanding perceptions of identity. Participants wanted product experiences that would support an increased sense of their own potential. Georgia wanted her product to give her the sense that she could “go anywhere and learn anything.” Cathy wanted her product to “help me connect where I’ve come from to where I want to go...and how to get there.” Jim wanted his product to “shake me up now and then... I’m kind of lazy...there are a lot of things I’d like to change.”

Communicating aspects of the self. When asked about using their device with others, participants were both reticent to reveal its contents while also seeing the product as a useful tool for sharing highly valued aspects of themselves. In regard to privacy, Georgia said, “They couldn’t use mine, because its content is programmed specifically to me... it’s private to me.”

Jim echoed this concern, suggesting that “I guess I would be careful about who I showed it to...there’s some pretty personal stuff there.”

At the same time, participants saw their devices serving as a tool to show others “who I truly am.” Jim in particular commented at length about this product usage. “It would be like a diary...having things about my life that were important to me...helping me keep track of those things... I could share some of that with friends...not just tell them stuff about me that they don’t know about, but show them too...that would be great.”

Bridging the product use experience with “lived” experience. All three participants saw their products as helping them engage the world in new and different ways. Georgia described how the technology would “take me out of myself” and would help her experience “an immediacy that doesn’t remove me from the world but let’s me move through the world.” Cathy wanted a device that “encouraged me to set it down and engage my environment...something that said ‘Put me down and be present to what’s going on.’” Jim wanted the device to “help me take chances...try new things out...find out what’s really out there.” These comments suggest that these participants wanted a device that would help them question perceptions of their life situations in order to perceive these situations differently.

Two of the participants also doubted whether such a bridging was possible or easy to manage. Georgia, describing the difference between the photos she selected for her collage and her typical experience with digital products, said “Technology can also handcuff you...these pictures make (personally meaningful experience) poignant, tangible...but technology is not as lived.” Cathy suggested that it could be “awkward to have a mechanical thing that had to do with (personally meaningful experience).” She was concerned with “not knowing how to do it,” not knowing how to make the bridge between device-triggered experience and real world experience.

Making meaning out of meaningless situations. When asked where they would use their device, two of the participants suggested times and places which they perceived as meaningless. Cathy talked about standing in line at the post office and the grocery store and “making something good out of hanging out and waiting.” Georgia wanted the device to help her be “surprised and excited about things that were mundane.”

Product features

Software qualities. Participants were asked to draw their products and describe the features that would help generate personally meaningful experience. Cathy spoke of product features that are currently available in cell phones and PDA's, including viewing photos and video, listening to audio files, and recording and viewing text. The other two participants spoke about new combinations of features. Georgia wanted a product that would serve as a multimedia blog: "I could have files on the thing and on the Web...publishing my day as I went along...choosing what to share and what to keep to myself." Jim wanted "something like project software, but it would be about me...not about a project."

Product design qualities. Participants had strong views about the design of the potential products. All three were concerned about the need to carry around yet one more device. Two participants suggested that the device be multi-modal, Cathy suggesting that it could replace her telephone and PDA, with added functionalities. Georgia said, "My pockets are already full with a cell phone and an iPod...I wouldn't want one more thing to dig out." She also wanted the device to be wearable so it "wouldn't be something I unpacked." Cathy also wanted the product design to be significantly different from current digital products. "It might have a textural feel such that holding it...it doesn't feel like metal... different from my phone and my palm pilot...it can't feel like an electronic device."

Discussion

The three participants of this pilot study described highly valued and deeply personal experiences that they would want from interaction with a digital product. These participants also described concrete situations in which they would employ a digital device to construct, maintain or modify life meanings. These findings suggest that a market exists for products that completely or partially support personally meaningful experience.

The next phase of this research will include a greater number of participants, a more diverse participant pool, and longer, more in-depth interviews in order to uncover richer and more nuanced understandings. One central goal of this study is the formulation of design principles that could describe the design space for products that support personally meaningful experience. A richer and more diverse dataset would be required to formulate such principles. The benefits to society from further investigating this research area are potentially wide-

ranging. As our society increasingly embraces digital technologies to perform common personal tasks, products which afford positive experiences of self-worth, an increased sense of effectiveness, or stimulate new realizations about personal values will be both useful and needed.

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